

A Study on English Translation of Allan H. Barr's Reconstruction of the Literariness of Contemporary Chinese Literature-A Case Study of the English Translation of Yu's Four Fictional Works

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Abstract

This study adopted the English translations of Yu's four fictional works, namely *The Seventh Day*, *Cries in the Drizzle*, *Boy in the Twilight: Stories of the Hidden China*, and *The April 3rd Incident: Stories*, by Allan H. Barr, along with their corresponding original texts as the corpora. Drawing on the theoretical perspectives of interdisciplinary fields such as linguistics, stylistics, and literary theory, it probed into the approaches and methods by which Barr reconstructed the literariness of the original works from the two aspects of theme presentation and rhetorical device conversion. Research findings demonstrate that through his translation efforts, the literariness of the original works has been enhanced and reshaped. His English translation strategies and methods for reshaping the literariness offered valuable references for the translation of contemporary Chinese literature into foreign languages. In terms of presenting themes, he adopted the translation strategy of intensifying the themes of originals and chose appropriate translation methods to reinforce those themes. As far as the translation of rhetorical devices is concerned, he preferred to adopt the homogeneous or heterogeneous transformation of rhetoric cognition. Additionally, he skillfully transforms the conceptual cognitive discourses of originals into rhetorical cognitive discourses, thus enhancing the rhetorical effects and literariness of the translations.

Keywords: Allan H. Barr; literariness; English translations of contemporary Chinese literature; strategies and methods.

1. Introduction

Allan H. Barr is a renowned British sinologist and translator who received his doctoral degree in Ming and Qing literature from Oxford University, specializing in the research of Pu Songling and *Strange Tales from a Chinese Studio*. He currently serves as the chair and professor of the Department of Asian Languages and Literatures at Pomona College in California, USA. Barr has translated five works by Yu and has a long-term cooperation with the author. His translations have been widely acclaimed, as Zhu et al. (2017: 76-77) have pointed out, among which *Boy in the Twilight: Stories of the Hidden China* ranked second in the most influential translated contemporary Chinese literary works in 2014, and *China in Ten Words* has been "collected by 1,152 libraries globally and received significant attention from American media" (Zhu et al., 2017: 77). What has made Barr's translations so well-received? This is closely related to his unique translator style (Liu & Huang, 2024) and his proposed translation goals of "conciseness, precision, fluency, and vividness" (Yang, 2019). Based on his outstanding performance in the field of translation, one cannot help but wonder: what strategies and methods has he employed in his English translations? This question undoubtedly deserves high attention from academia and warrants in-depth exploration.

The translation community has consistently focused on the study of Barr's translation strategies. For instance, Zhou (2015) examined his translation strategies for popular expressions in the English version of *China in Ten Words*, pointing out issues such as insufficient literariness and inconsistent terminology. Liu (2015) based on intertextuality theory,

combined with examples from Barr's English translation of *Cries in the Drizzle*, discussed his translation strategies and principles of intertextual translation. Zhu and Luo (2015) used Barr's English translations of *Cries in the Drizzle* and *Boy in the Twilight* as corpus materials, concluding that he primarily adopted domestication strategies while also employing methods of omission, addition, and free translation. Cui (2019) applied field theory and the concept of translator habitus, based on Barr's English translation of *The Seventh Day*, to analyze and summarize Barr's habitual translation strategies for idioms and colloquialisms.

In summary, these studies have generally examined three aspects: culturally loaded words (Zhu & Luo, 2015), popular expressions (Zhou, 2015), and idiomatic expressions (Wang & Cui, 2019; Zhu & Luo, 2015), while lacking attention to his translation strategies and methods for reshaping the literariness of the original works. Furthermore, these studies mostly revolve around the single translation by Barr, analyzing and inferring his preferred English translation strategies, while neglecting his strategies in other works. Obviously, these studies are limited by incomplete corpus materials and are far from sufficient for an in-depth interpretation of Barr's translation strategies.

"The image of Chinese literature overseas depends largely on the literary value and artistic level presented by the translations, which is inseparable from the literariness of the translated works" (Sun & Nie, 2022: 89). It is evident that a translator's recreation of the literariness of the original work helps to enhance the image of Chinese literature overseas, thereby promoting its dissemination and acceptance in the Western world. The reason why Barr's translations have been widely acclaimed is closely related to his literary aesthetic views and his emphasis on recreating the literariness of the translations. Therefore, this study takes all of Barr's translations of fictional works (four works) as research materials, drawing on the theoretical perspectives of interdisciplinary fields such as linguistics, stylistics, and literary theory, to explore his strategies and methods for reshaping literariness.

2. Interpretation of Literariness

In the field of literary studies, the concept of "literariness" is crucial and rich in connotation. It was first proposed by the Russian formalist critic Roman Jakobson, referring to the characteristics of literature. Jakobson pointed out that "the object of literary science is not literature, but 'literariness', which is the key element that makes a work a literary work" (quoted from Lemon and Reis, 1965: 107). Furthermore, he elaborated on the manifestations of literariness, considering it to be a transformation, intensification, or distortion of ordinary language. Viktor Shklovsky, from the same school, interpreted literariness as the "defamiliarization" of everyday language, while Boris Tomashevsky had unique insights in the discussion of literariness, emphasizing the importance of "rhythmic cadence" for literariness (quoted from Lemon and Reis, 1965: 13; 127). It is not difficult to see that the Russian Formalist school clearly tended to approach the essence of literariness from the perspectives of language and rhetoric when interpreting it.

However, different academic schools have different views. Symbolist poets believed that imagery is the main manifestation of literariness (quoted from Lemon and Reis, 1965: 5). Shi (2000: 127) proposed that literariness exists in narration, imagery, symbolism, function, structure, and aesthetic treatment, among various aspects. Tong (2009: 56-57) understood literariness from the perspective of literary aesthetic features, pointing out that it is embodied in the "breath", "mood", "atmosphere", and "rhythm" presented in the work.

Chinese and Western scholars have defined literariness from their respective perspectives, fully demonstrating the diversity and complexity of the concept of literariness. However, as Zhou (2003: 52) pointed out, since the connotation and extension of literature itself are always in dynamic change, it is indeed difficult to completely and comprehensively define literariness.

Against this academic background, this study, based on the many definitions and interpretations of literariness by predecessors, believes that literariness is embedded in various aspects of a work, such as theme expression, character and psychological description, imagery expression, rhetorical expression, cultural imagery, and the artistic treatment involved in the structure of the work. Moreover, in order to deeply analyze issues related to the English translation of literariness, this study starts from the aspects of theme presentation and rhetorical device conversion to analyze Barr's strategies and methods for reshaping the literariness of the original works.

3. Strategies and Methods for Reshaping Literariness

3.1 Theme Reshaping Strategies

Theme is the core content or central idea expressed in literary works and narrative literature. The theme of a novel is "the result of the writer's experience, perception, and analysis of social life, a concentrated reflection of the writer's understanding and evaluation of life. The theme of a novel is the soul of the work, determining the thought, spiritual height, social significance, and artistic quality of the work" (Wang et al., 1991; Ouyang, 2006: 23; Cao, 2010: 102). Evidently, the theme is the embodiment of the central idea of a work, like the main melody with distinctive features in a

piece of music, playing a "commanding" role over other melodies in the piece. For translators, how to accurately convey the thematic ideas of the work in the translation relates to the expression of the spirit or "soul" of the original work. However, the literary aesthetic views held by translators, the reading expectations of the target readers, and other factors will affect the translators' selection and translation treatment of thematic content, inevitably resulting in theme dilution, theme reproduction, or theme enhancement.

The themes of suffering and good versus evil are the mother propositions in Yu's novels. Representative works of these themes include *Cries in the Drizzle*, *The Seventh Day*, *To Live*, *Chronicle of a Blood Merchant*, and *Boy in the Twilight* (Zhang, 1999; Sun, 2012; Xie, 2017). Since *To Live* and *Chronicle of a Blood Merchant* were not translated by Barr, they are excluded from this study. Accordingly, this study uses the four fictional works translated by Barr—*The Seventh Day*, *Cries in the Drizzle*, *Boy in the Twilight*, and *The April 3rd Incident*—and their corresponding original texts as corpus materials to examine his habitual theme translation strategies from the perspectives of suffering and good versus evil themes, combined with specific examples for analysis and discussion.

3.1.1 Enhancement of the Suffering Theme

"Suffering is the theme of Yu's novels in the 1990s" (Chang & Ye, 2001: 96; Lü, 2013: 137). For example, the protagonist Sun Guanglin in *Cries in the Drizzle* experienced suffering from childhood to adulthood (Lü, 2013: 138). *The Seventh Day* portrays the diverse sufferings of the lower-class people (Liu, 2016: 95). It can be said that the theme of suffering permeates almost all of Yu's fiction writing. The extensive writing on "suffering" demonstrates Yu's deep reflection on the meaning and value of human existence (Cui, 2006: 122). How translators present the author's philosophical reflections on the suffering and value of life in their translations concerns the recreation and transmission of the suffering theme and literariness of the original work.

Research has found that Barr mainly adopts enhancement translation strategies to present the suffering theme in the original works, and guided by this strategy, he chooses two translation methods (perspective transformation and addition) to achieve his translation goals.

(1) Perspective Transformation Method

Example 1: 我看到父亲粗壮的巴掌打向了弟弟稚嫩的脸，我弟弟的身体被扔掉般的摔出去倒在地上。孙光明无声无息地躺在那里，似乎有很长时间。我的母亲，在父亲怒火面前和我一样害怕的母亲，那时惊叫着跑向我弟弟(Yu, 2004: 169)

My little brother's tender face took the full force of my father's failing hand. He flew through the air and landed with a thump on the floor, where he lay in total silence for what seemed like forever. My mother, no less frightened than me by my father's rampages, cried out in alarm and ran to his aid. (Yu, 2007: 176-177)

This example is selected from *The Seventh Day*, where "my four-year-old brother" was beaten severely by his father due to being mistakenly accused of breaking a small bowl in the house. To highlight that "my brother" was the direct victim of his father's violence, Barr first changed the first-person subject "I" in the original text to the third-person subject "My little brother's tender face", which serves to adjust the narrative distance because "the advantage of the third-person form is: the absence of 'I' will make readers feel there is no explicit 'you'". Therefore, the narrative is presented directly to readers without any medium (Leech & Short, 2007: 213), allowing the target readers to directly perceive the father's violence from the "brother's" perspective. Then, "我弟弟的身体被扔掉般的摔出去倒在地上" was not translated conventionally as "My brother's body was thrown out and fell to the ground", but was translated as "He flew through the air and landed with a thump on the floor" (meaning: One slap threw him into the air, and he landed on the floor with a thump). This has profound significance: "flew through the air" fully exposes the father's brutality in abusing his son, and "a thump" adds a sound effect not present in the original text, making the target readers seem to hear the sound of the body falling, enhancing the performative effect of the text. Barr's creation of images and sound effects increases the suffering narrative and prompts target readers to reflect: the father's brutality makes every member of the family a victim of suffering. Overall, Barr uses perspective transformation to adjust the reader's perception angle, as well as free translation enhancement to enrich the expressiveness of the translation, enhancing the emotional and situational conveyance effect.

(2) Addition

Example 2: 伍超在阳光里醒来，在月光里睡着。在这个城市里，他很久没有这样的生活了，差不多有一年多，他在既没有阳光也没有月光的地下醒来和睡着(Yu, 2013: 193)

Wu Chao woke up in sunlight and fell asleep by moonlight-sensations long denied him, since for a year or more he had woken and slept in an underground world with neither sun nor moon. (Yu, 2015: 183)

This example is selected from *The Seventh Day*. The character Wu Chao sold his own kidney to buy a cemetery plot for his girlfriend who committed suicide. Because he had to undergo kidney removal surgery, he was able to lie in a regular room, whereas previously he had been living in a basement. This "waking up in sunlight and falling asleep in moonlight", which is the most normal life for ordinary people, became a luxury for him. To highlight this suffering narrative, Barr added a dash to extend this psychological feeling of suffering, then added the translation "sensations long denied him", reflecting Wu Chao's long-term poor living environment, highlighting his impoverished and humble life, and strengthening the suffering narrative tendency.

3.1.2 Enhancement of the Good versus Evil Theme

The theme of good versus evil is one of the mother themes for many writers in their literary creations, with inspiration typically coming from the good and evil thoughts and behaviors exhibited by individuals in social life. Yu (2014: 166-167) had his own reflections on creation and human nature in *Hypocritical Works*, mentioning the covering up of the complexity of human nature by civilized order and common sense. Almost every one of his works is filled with the ugliness of human nature and the goodness that persists in human nature, providing "a new reference for contemporary literature's complex understanding of human nature" (Xie, 2004: 181). For the presentation of this theme, Barr also adopted enhancement translation strategies, and guided by this translation strategy, he employed three translation methods (rewriting, font variation, and syntactic transformation) to achieve his translation goals.

(1) Rewriting

Lefevere (1992: 14) mentioned: "Literary works that have not undergone any form of rewriting might sink into the river of history after a few years or even months after their publication." In the process of theme translation, Barr rewrote the narrative content of the original text by selecting evaluative derogatory adjectives, derogatory nouns, and nouns with ironic meanings, which implicitly formed the translator's narrative evaluation of human good and evil, highlighting the good versus evil theme of the original text. Aldrich N. J. et al. consider "narrative evaluation refers to the evaluator's evaluation or view of the people and things narrated in the story" (quoted from Li & Wang, 2017: 96), including "evaluative adjectives, evaluative adverbs, evaluation in terms of degree, bodily or emotional feelings with high evaluative implications, emphatic repetition, etc." (Wang et al., 2016: 50). When discussing the subtleties of the author's tone, Leech and Short mentioned that "evaluative terms and evaluative inferences in narrative discourse can embody the stance or attitude adopted by the author" (Leech & Short, 2007: 225-227). Translation is also a form of narrative, and translators' selection of evaluative adjectives or nouns with evaluative meanings in the translation process can reveal their implicit stance and attitude. Therefore, Barr's purpose in rewriting the original text by selecting evaluative adjectives and derogatory nouns is to permeate his own evaluation and attitude toward human good and evil into the translation, thereby revealing the ugly behaviors of the characters in the novel.

Example 3: 当英花提着水桶走去时,我父亲满脸通红,发出了响亮的咳嗽声,这个**痨病鬼**在那个时刻,村里有人在不远处走动的时刻,他的手捏住了英花短裤上的大红花案,以及里面的皮肉。(Yu, 2004: 57)

As Yinghua walked over, bucket in hand, my father flushed and gave a loud cough. Although villagers were walking by not far away, the incorrigible lecher put his hands on the big red flowers on Yinghua's shorts and on the flesh underneath. (Yu, 2007: 61)

Example 3 is selected from *Cries in the Drizzle*, where the original text describes the process of Sun Guangcai raping his daughter-in-law in broad daylight when his son was not at home. Barr translated the original term "痨病鬼" into the evaluative phrase "incorrigible lecher" (meaning an incurable lecher). The use of the evaluative noun "lecher" means "labeling the described object, permanently attributing it to the described object" (Xin, 2005: 70), forming a powerful narrative intervention that clearly expresses the translator's attitude and evaluation of the character, thereby influencing the target readers' understanding of the character Sun Guangcai, namely, a "beast-hearted 'father' who raped his daughter-in-law regardless of ethics and morality", while also highlighting his despicable image.

Example 4: 我的同学那时的年龄显然无法立刻领会其间的严酷,国庆傻乎乎地看着他的父亲。这个**混帐男人**留下了十元钱和二十斤粮票后,就提起两只篮子下楼了。(Yu, 2004: 221)

Guoqing was too young to appreciate all the grim implications, and he just looked at his father in bewilderment. The heartless bridegroom-to-be left his son ten yuan in cash and twenty pounds' worth of grain coupons, picked up a couple of baskets, and went downstairs. (Yu, 2007: 229)

Example 4 is selected from *Cries in the Drizzle*. The phrase "混帐男人" in the original text refers to Guoqing's father, who abandoned his son Guoqing after he remarried following the death of Guoqing's mother. Barr translated the original phrase "混帐男人" into "heartless bridegroom-to-be", with the evaluative adjective "heartless" and the ironic noun "bridegroom-to-be" strongly satirizing Guoqing's father's coldness and heartlessness in abandoning his only son for the sake of remarriage, giving a feeling of being "worse than an animal", revealing the dark side of human selfishness and cruelty.

(2) Font Variation

Example 5: 他们问我：“来发，你妈是怎么死的？”(Yu, 1999: 6)

"LAIFA, HOW DID YOUR MOM DIE?" they asked. (Yu, 2014: 7)

Example 5 is selected from *Boy in the Twilight*. "Laifa" in the original text is a fool, and the people around him ridicule and insult him in various ways, such as "asking how Laifa's mother died". Anyone would find the loss of a loved one painful and would try to avoid facing the fact of losing a close relative. However, the people around Laifa showed no regard for such questions, with mockery and amusement hiding cruelty and indifference. "Visual structure reflects a certain ideology and plays a key role in semantic construction" (Kress & Leeuwen, 2006: 47). For the slanderous speech of evil characters, Barr capitalized them all, constructing the visual structure of the translation through font variation, which plays an important role in understanding the characters in the novel and the overall meaning of the work, prompting target readers to reflect on human hypocrisy and cruelty, thus deepening the narrative of human evil.

(3) Syntactic Transformation

1) Converting Declarative Sentences into Rhetorical Questions

Barr changed the narrative discourse of the ugly characters in the novel from declarative sentences to rhetorical questions, to contrast the shamelessness and rascality of the ugly characters after doing evil, as shown in the following example:

Example 6: 我父亲怒气冲冲地大声喊叫：哪有这样不讲理的，我不就是替我儿子摸摸她身子骨结实不结实，就把我打成这样子。” (Yu, 2004: 54)

My father was outraged. "Those people are so unreasonable!" he cried. "I was just trying to look out for my son and make sure the girl was in good health. Can you believe how bad they beat me up?" (Yu, 2007: 59)

This example is taken from *Cries in the Drizzle*, and it describes the sophistry of "my father"(Sun Guangcai) in front of his son. The truth of the matter is that Sun Guangcai was beaten and scolded by the girl's family after he molested his future daughter-in-law. Barr converted the declarative sentence "就把我打成这样子" into the rhetorical question "Can you believe how bad they beat me up?" because "rhetorical questions can directly attract readers" (Leech & Short, 2007: 227), and "rhetorical questions are more assertive and powerful than declarative sentences, and can better express strong emotions" (Zhang, 2008: 62). This questioning tone powerfully portrays Sun Guangcai's despicable image of "the guilty party playing the victim," making target readers feel that his behavior has seriously lost the ethics and morality of being a father, implicitly highlighting the evil in human nature.

2) Converting Declarative Sentences into Emphatic Sentences

Example 7: 他是那样羞愧和疼爱地望着我，我曾经有过这样一位父亲。可我当时并没有这样的感受，他死后我回到南门以后的日子，我才渐渐意识到这一点，比起孙广才来，王立强在很多地方都更像父亲。(Yu, 2004: 276)

He gazed at me with such shame and affection that I say to myself: yes, I did have a father like that. But that was not how I responded at the time: it was only after he died, when I was back in South-gate, that I gradually became aware that Wang Liqiang was much more of a father to me than Sun Kwangtsai. (Yu, 2007: 285)

Example 7 is selected from *Cries in the Drizzle*. In the translation, Barr used the auxiliary verb "did" to emphasize the sentence, emphasizing "my" recognition of my adoptive father in the original text; then he used the English emphatic sentence structure "it was only after...when...than Sun Kwangtsai" to highlight the huge contrast between "my" circumstances after returning to South-gate after the foster father's death and the previous brief happiness. Facing the beatings and insults from his biological father Sun Guangcai, "I" now felt that my adoptive father was more like a father. Through Barr's translation, the kind and loving adoptive father is sharply contrasted with the selfish and brutal biological father. Meanwhile, it also deepens the thematic tendency of the good and evil of human nature.

3.2 Methods for Translating Rhetorical Devices

"Rhetorical devices are novel expressions used to enhance the expressive effect of language" (Wang, 2004: 11), or it can be said that they are forms of speech that deviate from linguistic norms (Diao et al., 1990). The skillful use of rhetorical devices in literary works can enhance the expressive charm of language, increase readers' sense of defamiliarization and novelty, more powerfully shape the personality traits of characters, effectively promote the development of the plot, and even achieve the effect of deepening the theme. Therefore, accurately translating the rhetorical devices in the original work is crucial, related to the understanding of narrative content, the shaping of character personalities, the development of the plot, the interpretation of the theme, and even the reshaping of the literariness of the original work.

Currently, the main methods for translating rhetorical devices include literal translation, free translation, conversion, and derivation (Liang, 2007: 18). Different from traditional methods for translating rhetorical devices, this study borrows the concepts of rhetorical cognition and conceptual cognition (Tan et al., 2006: 23) to explore Barr's conversion methods for translating rhetorical devices.

Rhetorical cognition and conceptual cognition are two main ways for humans to recognize and represent the world (Tan et al., 2006: 23). "Conceptual cognition refers to the commonality of things with a prescribed semantic orientation, embodying the logical relationship of things with conceptual combinations in the support of logical contexts, which is a universal way for humans to grasp and cognize the world" (ibid.: 23). In other words, conceptual cognition locks onto objects in a conceptualized way, rationally approaching the universal meaning of cognitive objects. "Rhetorical cognition often deviates from the conventional semantics of things, dissolving the universality of conceptual cognition in the support of aesthetic contexts, departing from the logical relationship of things, stimulating sensory experiences, and it is a subjectified way of cognition. In short, rhetorical cognition understands objects in an aestheticized way, activating the subject's sense of novelty to re-perceive objects" (ibid.: 23). In cognitive activities, people often convert conceptual cognition into rhetorical cognition (ibid.: 23). Research has found that for the translation of rhetorical devices, Barr not only adopts homogeneous conversion of rhetorical cognition but also uses heterogeneous conversion of rhetorical cognition and conversion of conceptual cognition to rhetorical cognition to enhance the literariness of the original work.

(1) Homogeneous Conversion of Rhetorical Devices

Example 8: 街道上的雨水依然在哗哗流动，他向前走时，感受着水花在脚上纷纷开放与纷纷凋谢。(Yu, 1995: 244)

Water was still eddying, and as he advanced, he felt flowers of foam blossoming and withering at his feet. (Yu, 2018: 174)

This example is selected from *The April 3rd Incident*. The phrase "开放" and "凋谢" in the original text are generally used to describe the blooming and withering of flowers, but here they are used to describe the state of "water splash" bouncing onto the feet and sliding down from the feet. This expression is clearly a variation and deviation from everyday language. Barr translated it as "flowers of foam blossoming and withering at his feet", achieving a homogeneous conversion of foregrounded rhetoric, recreating the artistry of the original language.

(2) Heterogeneous Conversion of Rhetorical Cognition

There are three main reasons for heterogeneous conversion of rhetorical cognition in literary translation: firstly, it is impossible to find an appropriate homogeneous transformation in the target language; secondly, the target language readers cannot accept the homogeneous transformation of rhetorical cognition in the original text; thirdly, compared with homogeneous transformation, heterogeneous transformation can better enhance the literariness of the translated text (Feng, 2017b: 131). Through a close reading of the text, this study has found that Barr mostly carried out heterogeneous transformations of the rhetorical discourse in the original text with the aim of enhancing the literariness of the translated text, as shown in the following examples:

Example 9: 那动作像是虾钳一样迅速。(Yu, 1999: 36)

His elbow twitched with the speed of a lobster's pincers. (Yu, 2014: 35)

Example 9 is selected from *Boy in the Twilight*. The phrase "像是虾钳" in the original text is a metaphorical rhetoric, describing the dexterity of the character Ma'er eating shrimp. Barr used "the speed of a lobster's pincers" to convert the metaphorical rhetoric of the original text into transferred epithet rhetoric, which is a heterogeneous conversion of rhetorical cognition. The adoption of transferred epithet rhetoric increases the strangeness and novelty of language, to some extent enhancing the rhetoric and literariness of the original text.

Example 10: 我现在回顾他当初的背影时，已经像一个阴影一样虚无了。(Yu, 2004: 167)

When I try now to recall the image of him standing there, I see only a hazy shadow. (Yu, 2007: 175)

In this example, the expression "像一个阴影一样虚无" in the original text is metaphorical rhetoric. Barr used "only a hazy shadow" to convert it into hyperbolic rhetoric, which is a heterogeneous conversion of rhetorical cognition. The hyperbolic rhetoric in the translation highlights the image characteristics of the character Sun Youyuan, who became weak and timid due to long-term abuse by his son. Compared with the original text, the hyperbolic rhetoric has a more vivid and expressive effect, enabling readers of the translated text to better understand and grasp the character traits in the novel.

(3) Conversion of Conceptual Cognition to Rhetorical Cognition

Conversion of conceptual cognition to rhetorical cognition in translation refers to the translator converting conceptual cognitive discourse in the original text into rhetorical cognitive discourse, or adding some rhetorical discourse to the original text. These rhetorical discourses include metaphor, hyperbole, personification, metonymy, etc. Although Barr is a translator with high fidelity to original texts, he never translates mechanically or rigidly. As he said, "re-create the various feelings that the original brings to its readers" (Barr, 2011: 33), such as "adding details not present in the original text as appropriate to achieve the artistic effect I deem necessary" (ibid.: 35-36). This can be understood as an exploration and attempt at creativity in translation, seeking to recreate or even surpass the artistry and literariness of the original text. George Steiner once proposed the idea of translations surpassing the original, citing Baudelaire's translated poem "The Bridge of Sighs" and Santayana's translated poem "Art" as examples (Steiner, 2001: 423). The practice of converting conceptual cognitive discourse into rhetorical cognitive discourse in translation can be seen as a transcendence of the original work, a transcendence requires the translator to possess both keen rhetorical appreciation and a creative spirit to break through the original work. Below, we will explore how Barr converts conceptual cognitive discourse in the original text into rhetorical cognitive discourse through examples.

Example 11: 显然他还在向他的父母讲述，可是他的父母站在那里一动不动。(Yu, 1999: 135)

It was clear there was no end of things he wanted to tell his parents, but they just stood there like statues. (Yu, 2014: 151)

Example 11 is selected from *Boy in the Twilight*. The expression of "站在那里一动不动" in the original text belongs to conceptual cognitive discourse. Barr added a metaphorical image "like statues" in the translation, transforming it into rhetorical cognitive discourse. Thus, the image of characters standing motionless like statues jumps off the page, invisibly enhancing the literariness of the translation.

Example 12: 这时候我脑袋热得直冒汗，我的情绪极其激昂，也就是说我已经昏了头了。(Yu, 1999: 164)

My head was about to explode, I was so carried away. I was out of my mind now. (Yu, 2014: 178)

This example is selected from *Boy in the Twilight*, describing "my" anger and helplessness when explaining to a friend to no avail. The expression of "我脑袋热得直冒汗" in the original text belongs to conceptual cognitive discourse. Barr translated it as "My head was about to explode," transforming it into hyperbolic rhetorical discourse, more vividly reflecting the emotional characteristics of the character in the novel, enhancing the literariness of the translation.

4. Conclusion

In the current context of Chinese literature actively seeking to "go global", whether Chinese literature can be effectively disseminated and accepted in the Western world is closely related to the transmission of its literariness. This means that the translator's responsibility should not be limited to ensuring the fidelity of the translation to the original text, but should also focus on the issue of reshaping literariness in the translation process. This article focuses on Barr's research on reshaping literariness in English translation, deeply discussing the strategies and specific methods he used for reshaping literariness from two important aspects: theme presentation and rhetorical device conversion.

In terms of theme presentation, the research found that Barr uses enhancement translation strategies when dealing with fictional works. Guided by this strategy, he carefully selects five translation methods, including rewriting of the original narrative content, adding narrative content, using perspective transformation methods, making syntactic level transformations, and using font variation methods. Through the comprehensive application of these methods, themes such as suffering and good versus evil in the original works are enhanced to varying degrees in the translations, enabling the translations to more powerfully convey the core thematic ideas of the original works. In terms of rhetorical device translation, Barr, out of consideration for enhancing the literariness of the translations, engages in flexible and diverse conversions of the rhetorical discourse in the original texts. On one hand, he carries out homogeneous or heterogeneous conversions of the rhetorical discourse in the original texts based on specific situations; on the other hand, to effectively compensate for the possible loss of the rhetoric in the original texts in the translation process, he ingeniously converts the

conceptual cognitive discourse of the original texts into rhetorical cognitive discourse. In this way, the rhetorical effect of the translations is significantly enhanced, and the literariness is further improved.

The reason why Barr's translations have been widely acclaimed is certainly related to his skillful translation techniques and his deep understanding of Western culture and reader tastes, but more critically, it is because, with his keen literary appreciation ability, he always pays high attention to the artistic effect of the translations, and thus attaches great importance to reshaping literariness in the translation process. Overall, the translation strategies and methods used by Barr play an important role in strengthening the thematic narrative, rhetorical effect, and literariness of the translations, while also greatly enhancing the readability of the translations. This undoubtedly has very important reference significance for the translation of Chinese contemporary literature into foreign languages.

It should be noted that this article focuses on discussion of the issue of English translation of the literariness of Chinese literary works from two aspects: theme presentation and rhetorical device conversion, with the aim of serving as a starting point for further discussion. In fact, literariness is embodied in many aspects of a work, including theme expression, character and psychological description, imagery expression, and rhetorical expression, among various artistic techniques. Thus, to deeply explore the issue of English translation of literariness, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive examination from multiple dimensions and perspectives, and conclusions cannot be hastily drawn based on a single perspective. Obviously, this topic still needs to be further explored in our subsequent research.

Funding

This research is supported by General Project of Humanities and Social Sciences: Sinologist Allan H. Barr's Translator Style Research Project, Guangxi Minzu University under Grant No. 2022MDSKYB04.

This research is also supported by the Guangxi Minzu University 2024 Talent Recruitment Research Start-up Project: Allan H. Barr's Reconstruction of the Literariness in the English Translation of Contemporary Chinese Literature under Grant No. 2024SKQD38.

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